

Focus

Difficulty staying focused

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Easy to use app?

Help?

A platform for help and support videos?

Focus

**Cognitive
overload in the
presence of
complex
interfaces or too
much information**

Existing tools

Immersive
Reader

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Help?

Simpler
processes?

Focus

**Cognitive
overload from
pop ups and
others
distractions**

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Help?

Simpler
processes?

Focus

**Delayed
processing:
additional time
required to take
in and understand
information**

Existing tools

**Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...**

What would help?

**Simpler
processes?**

Help?

Focus

Fatigue

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Simpler processes?

Help?

